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The Theory and Practice of Post-Conflict Transformation: Navigating the Interplay Between Reintegration and Justice

The societies that fall into post-conflict mode are challenged by the need to create trust, rehabilitate institutions, and provide guarantees that such brutal experiences do not return. This process – referred to as post-conflict transformation – goes far beyond the mere physical rebuilding of the country. It is psychological, social, and political healing from the wounds opened by conflict. There are two aspects of reconciliation: reintegration and justice, and the two sometimes conflict. Although reintegration focuses on social stability and the re-socialization of former combatants into civil society, justice aims at achieving accountability for mass violence and the recognition of victims' rights. Favoring one over the other can risk undermining the prospects for longer-term peace. The big question in post-conflict societies, then, is: Can we reconcile justice and reintegration in such a way that facilitates both peace and accountability?

The peace and conflict studies field provides a number of concepts to comprehend post-conflict transition. It contrasts negative peace (absence of direct violence) with positive peace (presence of justice, equality, and effective institutions) (Galtung, 1996). Post-conflict transformation doesn't just want to stop violence; it wants to create a positive peace. John Lederach (Lederach, 1997) focuses on relationship-building, local ownership, and cultural context in peacebuilding. He calls for a long-term transformation that includes grassroots involvement, mental healing, and structural change. The subfield of transitional justice – born of mass atrocities – provides a sharper focus on the way countries have responded to past abuse. Transitional justice, as formulated by the United Nations (2004), includes judicial and non-judicial mechanisms, such as prosecution, truth commissions, reparations, and institutional reform. The aim is to identify victims, restore trust in institutions, and prevent further violence.

The relationship between reintegration and justice is complex by its nature.

Social reintegration focuses on quick social stabilization. It includes demobilization, retraining of former fighters, psychological care, and reintegration into society. But this procedure can perhaps paradoxically understate demands for justice if the perpetrators are excluded but not held to account, in turn creating a feeling of impunity as well as bitterness among the victims. Justice, especially through prosecutions or truth-telling, acknowledges and undergirds the morality of

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victims' experiences, as it helps to pave the way for reconciliation. But it can undermine reintegration by instilling fear of retribution among former combatants or exacerbating social divisions in communities that don't universally support accountability. The trick then, is to find ways to reconcile these competing imperatives in ways that do not privilege one to the exclusion of the other.

Post-apartheid South Africa had the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC), a process that favored truth-telling and restorative justice over retribution. Those who had committed political violence could qualify for amnesty if they made a full confession of their crimes. Although the TRC facilitated national discussion and contributed to healing, it was also criticized for small material reparations and a lack of attention to economic injustices (Mamdani, 2002). Nevertheless, the TRC is often pointed to as an example of how effective reintegration and justice (justice not in terms of punishment but of reconciliation) can be.

Rwanda – which, like Nuremberg, is responding to a genocide – took a hybrid approach to justice, where formal tribunals (like the ICTR) operated in conjunction with Gacaca courts, traditional community-based justice. The Gacaca system enabled perpetrators to publicly confess and express regret, promoting reintegration through recognition of the harm inflicted. A community-based approach to justice that emphasizes self-determination and stakeholder responsibility is more consistent with indigenous peoples' values, knowledge, and traditions, and it has led to greater community involvement and diversion from the courts, at the same time as it has shown pro-civil rights protections and the possibility to entrench local power inequities (Clark, 2010). However, through Rwanda's example, it can be witnessed that local mechanisms have the potential for justice and reintegration integration, though not without consequences.

The current war in Ukraine is quite a clear example of this problem of post-conflict transformation. In Ukraine, there needs to be considerable effort to plan the repatriation and reintegration of internal refugees, as well as people from formerly occupied territories, including those who were informants. At the same time, there are massive calls for justice for war crimes committed by Russian forces.

Key questions include: how can Ukraine find the justice it needs without alienating reintegrating populations? How can one address not only the recognition of the victim but also possible future reconciliation? How can the state involve local communities in the process of transformation? Ukraine will need a solution that will be «principled, nuanced, and flexible, victim-centered, that will combine immediate social cohesiveness and a long-term focus on accountability.

The post-conflict transition does not have a one-size-fits-all model. The latter will have to be both context-specific and inclusive, as well as locally grounded for individual societies with the unique history and needs of each society. There should be no false dichotomy between justice and reintegration; rather, the processes are interdependent. There are circumstances in which justice delayed is justice required, but sometimes it is lost. Sustainable peace depends on the capacity of societies to reconstitute relationships, institutions, and narratives in a way that neither obliterates the memory of victims nor eliminates the truths of the past in favor of the pursuit of stability.

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